

MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE VIBRATION OF THE ELECTRIC MOTOR AND THE DEFECT IN THE BEARING

To‘xtasinov Davronbek Xoshimjon o‘g‘li

Senior Lecturer, Automation and control of technological processes, Namangan Institute of Engineering Technology, Namangan, Uzbekistan.

davronbek_toxtasinov@nammti.uz

Introduction. Electric motors are pivotal in various industrial applications, and their reliability is essential for uninterrupted operations. One of the most common causes of motor failure is defects in bearings. Bearings, being crucial for the smooth rotation of the motor shaft, directly influence the vibration characteristics of the system when they develop defects. This study aims to establish a mathematical model that correlates the vibrations of an electric motor with bearing defects, providing a predictive tool for early fault detection and maintenance.

Keywords: Electric motor, bearing defects, vibration analysis, mathematical model, fault detection, predictive maintenance, defect frequencies, differential equation, Fourier transform.

Methods

System Parameters and Defect Characterization

We considered an electric motor where the rotor and shaft assembly are supported by bearings. Key parameters include:

m : Mass of the rotor and shaft.

k : Stiffness of the bearing.

c : Damping coefficient.

$F(t)$: External force due to bearing defects.

Bearing defects were categorized as inner race defects, outer race defects, rolling element defects, and cage defects. The force due to a defect, $F(t)$, was modeled based on the defect type and motor operating conditions.

Mathematical Model

Equation of Motion

The motion of the system was described by Newton's second law:

$$m\ddot{x}(t) + c\dot{x}(t) + kx(t) = F(t)$$

where $x(t)$ represents the displacement of the rotor.

Defect-Induced Force

The force $F(t)$ was modeled as a periodic function for repeated defects:

$$F(t) = F_0 \cos(2\pi f_d t) + F_1 \cos(4\pi f_d t) + \dots$$

where f_d is the defect frequency, related to the motor's rotational speed ω).

Characteristic Defect Frequencies

Defect frequencies were calculated as follows:

- Ball Pass Frequency on Inner Race (BPFI):

$$f_{BPFI} = \frac{n}{2} \left(1 + \frac{D}{d} \cos \theta \right) f_r$$

- Ball Pass Frequency on Outer Race (BPFO):

$$f_{BPFO} = \frac{n}{2} \left(1 - \frac{D}{d} \cos \theta \right) f_r$$

- Fundamental Train Frequency (FTF):

$$f_{FTF} = \frac{f_r}{2} \left(1 - \frac{D}{d} \cos \theta \right)$$

- Ball Spin Frequency (BSF):

$$f_{BSF} = \frac{d}{D} f_r \left(1 - \left(\frac{d}{D} \cos \theta \right)^2 \right)$$

where n is the number of rolling elements, D is the pitch diameter, d is the rolling element diameter, θ is the contact angle, and f_r is the rotational frequency.

Solution and Analysis

We solved the differential equation using numerical methods and performed Fourier transform on the time-domain solution to analyze the frequency domain response. This helped in identifying peaks at characteristic defect frequencies.

Results

The frequency response of the motor's vibration revealed distinct peaks at the calculated defect frequencies:

- Inner Race Defects showed prominent peaks at f_{BPFI} and its harmonics.
- Outer Race Defects exhibited peaks at f_{BPFO} and its harmonics.
- Rolling Element Defects produced peaks at f_{BSF} .
- Cage Defects were indicated by peaks at f_{FTF} .

The amplitude of these peaks correlated with the severity of the defects, providing a quantitative measure for defect diagnosis.

Discussion

The model successfully established a direct relationship between bearing defects and motor vibrations. By identifying characteristic frequencies, the model enables early detection of specific types of bearing defects. This predictive capability can

significantly enhance maintenance strategies, reducing downtime and extending the lifespan of electric motors.

Limitations

The model assumes linear behavior and does not account for nonlinearities in real-world applications. Future work should incorporate nonlinear dynamics and validate the model with extensive experimental data.

Implications

This model serves as a foundation for developing advanced diagnostic tools that can monitor motor vibrations in real-time, providing early warnings and preventing catastrophic failures in industrial settings.

Conclusion

We developed a robust mathematical model linking the vibrations of an electric motor to specific bearing defects. By leveraging characteristic defect frequencies, this model offers a powerful tool for early fault detection, enhancing the reliability and efficiency of electric motor operations. Future research should aim at refining the model and integrating it with real-time monitoring systems for practical applications.

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